

CO₂-EOR Optimization through Nanomaterial Integration: A Sustainable Approach

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ABSTRACT

The pursuit of efficient and sustainable oil production has spurred advancements in Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) techniques. Carbon Dioxide Enhanced Oil Recovery (CO₂-EOR) has gained prominence for its potential to boost hydrocarbon recovery and curtail the environmental impact of oil production. This research paper investigates the fusion of CO₂ with EOR, harnessing the transformative power of nanotechnology. Nanoparticles, with their size-dependent properties, offer a promising avenue for augmenting CO₂-based EOR. This study explores the nanoparticles that are experimented for reservoir conditions under CO₂-EOR method, addressing challenges and future concerns. The paper assesses the on-field reality of nanoparticle-enhanced CO₂-EOR methods. Environmental considerations are paramount, as nanotechnology minimizes CO₂ emissions, aligning with sustainability goals, enhancing industry competitiveness, and promoting a greener energy future.

Keywords

Nanotechnology, Enhanced Oil Recovery, Oil mobility, Hydrocarbon recovery, Sweep efficiency.

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1. Introduction

In the global quest for green and sustainable energy solutions, the oil industry is at a crossroads. Meeting the ever-increasing energy demands of our modern world while addressing pressing environmental concerns necessitates innovative strategies for oil production. In this context, the exploration of progressive techniques to extract trapped oil from reservoirs has taken center stage. Among these evolving methods, Carbon Dioxide Enhanced Oil Recovery (CO₂-EOR) has emerged as a prominent and promising approach that not only enhances hydrocarbon recovery but also contributes significantly to mitigating the environmental impact of oil production. Efficiently extracting trapped oil from reservoirs is of paramount importance [1]. Trapped oil represents a substantial portion of a reservoir's Oil Initially in Place (OIIP), which is the total volume of oil present before any extraction activities begin. OIIP serves as the reservoir's untapped potential. To put this in perspective, OIIP represents the entirety of oil available in a reservoir, and extracting it is crucial for several reasons:

1.1. Optimal Resource Utilization: Recovering trapped oil ensures the optimal utilization of hydrocarbon resources, making the most of what the reservoir has to offer.

1.2. Energy Security: Trapped oil reservoirs hold a significant portion of our energy reserves. Efficient extraction enhances energy security on both national and global scales.

1.3. Economic Sustainability: In many cases, trapped oil is economically viable, particularly in mature fields. Extracting this oil prolongs the economic viability of oil-producing regions. Of all the methods employed for hydrocarbon recovery, Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) methods constitute a substantial share of the OIIP production, often recovering two-thirds or more of the total OIIP. This remarkable contribution underscores the pivotal role EOR plays in unlocking the full potential of reservoirs [2].

CO₂-EOR, with its ability to significantly enhance recovery rates and extend the productive life of mature oil fields, leads the pack among EOR methods. Its promise lies not only in recovering trapped oil but also in reducing the carbon footprint associated with hydrocarbon production. The use of CO₂ for EOR aligns with carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) initiatives, making it an environmentally responsible approach to hydrocarbon extraction. However, the road to successful CO₂-EOR is not without challenges. Technical feasibility and environmental sustainability are paramount concerns that necessitate innovative solutions. This is where the transformative role of nanotechnology comes into play.

This paper embarks on a comprehensive exploration of the

synergy between CO₂-EOR and nanotechnology, with the aim of harnessing the transformative potential of nanoparticles to augment the efficiency and sustainability of hydrocarbon production. It delves into the development of nanoparticles explicitly designed for reservoir conditions, addressing critical questions of stability, compatibility, and reservoir interaction.

Moreover, as sustainability and environmental considerations occupy an increasingly central role in industry practices, this paper meticulously evaluates the environmental impact of nanoparticle-enhanced CO₂-EOR. By reducing CO₂ emissions, aligning with sustainability objectives, and enhancing industry competitiveness, this technique holds the promise of contributing substantively to a greener energy future [3].

In conclusion, the fusion of CO₂-EOR with nanotechnology represents an innovative and promising frontier in the pursuit of efficient and sustainable hydrocarbon production. As this research unfolds, it offers profound insights into the potential of nanoparticles to redefine the landscape of oil recovery, addressing environmental imperatives in an era where carbon capture and achieving net-zero emissions are paramount goals.

2. Overview of Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) Techniques:

The extraction of hydrocarbons from reservoirs has been a cornerstone of the global energy industry for decades. Traditional methods, known as primary and secondary recovery techniques, have enabled the production of significant volumes of crude oil. However, these methods often leave a substantial portion of oil trapped in reservoirs. Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) methods have emerged as innovative approaches to tap into these previously unrecoverable reserves [4]. EOR techniques go beyond the primary and secondary methods and offer a promising solution to maximize hydrocarbon production. In this overview, we will explore primary and secondary methods, their limitations, and why EOR is a more advantageous approach.

3. Limitations of Primary and Secondary Recovery Methods

3.1. Primary Recovery (Natural Drive): Primary recovery methods involve the exploitation of naturally occurring reservoir energy to push hydrocarbons to the surface. These methods, including the use of natural pressure and gravity, can only recover a fraction of the oil in a reservoir. Limitations include:

- Recovery rates typically range from 5% to 15% of the original oil in place.
- Oil flow diminishes as reservoir pressure declines.

- Reservoirs may become uneconomical to operate relatively quickly.

3.2. *Secondary Recovery (Waterflooding)*: Secondary recovery methods entail the injection of water or gas into reservoirs to displace oil and enhance production. While more effective than primary methods, they still have limitations:

- Waterflooding can only recover an additional 20% to 40% of the original oil in place.
- The injected water or gas can channel through the reservoir, leaving pockets of unrecovered oil.
- Secondary methods often require substantial water resources.

4. Advantages of Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) Methods

4.1. *Higher Recovery Rates*: EOR methods can recover a significantly higher percentage of the original oil in place, often exceeding 50%. This translates to more efficient resource utilization and increased production [5].

4.2. *Tailored Approaches*: EOR techniques are versatile and can be tailored to suit specific reservoir conditions. Different methods include:

- Gas Injection (CO₂ or Natural Gas)**: Injecting gases, such as carbon dioxide (CO₂) or natural gas, into reservoirs can increase oil mobility and enhance recovery rates. CO₂-EOR is particularly effective in altering the oil-water interface, making it easier to displace trapped oil.
- Chemical Injection (Polymers, Surfactants, Alkaline)**: Chemical agents can alter the fluid properties within the reservoir, reducing interfacial tension and improving oil displacement.
- Thermal Methods (Steam Injection)**: Raising the reservoir temperature with steam injection reduces oil viscosity, making it easier to flow and recover.

4.3. *Reservoir Pressure Maintenance*: EOR methods can help maintain or restore reservoir pressure, which not only enhances oil recovery but also extends the economic life of the field.

4.4. *Minimized Environmental Impact*: Some EOR methods, such as CO₂-EOR, can help reduce greenhouse gas emissions by sequestering CO₂ underground while simultaneously recovering oil.

4.5. *Economic Viability*: While EOR methods may require higher upfront investments, the increased oil recovery they provide often makes them economically viable, especially in mature fields where primary and secondary methods have exhausted their potential.

Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) methods offer a transformative approach to maximize hydrocarbon production [6]. While primary and secondary methods have limitations, EOR provides higher recovery rates, tailored approaches, reservoir pressure maintenance, and reduced environmental impact.

Figure 1. Different oil recovery stages with their recovery rates

5. Carbon Dioxide Enhanced Oil Recovery (CO₂-EOR)

In the realm of Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) techniques, Carbon Dioxide Enhanced Oil Recovery (CO₂-EOR) shines as a dynamic and sustainable approach to maximize hydrocarbon extraction [7]. This comprehensive introduction provides an in-depth understanding of CO₂-EOR as a specific EOR technique, elucidating its fundamental principles, mechanisms, and outlining the distinct advantages that set it apart from other EOR methods.

6. Fundamental Principles and Mechanisms of CO₂-EOR

6.1. *Remarkable Miscibility*: CO₂-EOR leverages the remarkable miscibility of carbon dioxide (CO₂) with crude oil. CO₂ exhibits an extraordinary degree of miscibility with oil, readily dissolving in the oil, significantly enhancing its mobility within the reservoir, and achieving oil recovery rates of over 50% of the original oil in place (OOIP).

Figure 2. Mechanism of CO₂-EOR

6.2. *Oil Swelling and Viscosity Reduction*: CO₂ possesses the unique property of causing oil to swell and reducing its viscosity. When CO₂ interacts with oil, it alters the oil's physical properties, reducing its viscosity by up to 50%. This reduction in viscosity allows the oil to flow more easily through the reservoir rock, maximizing recovery efficiency [8].

6.3. *Wettability Alteration*: CO₂ can modify the wettability of the reservoir rock, changing it from oil-wet to water-wet. This alteration enhances the displacement of oil by water, improving recovery efficiency further.

7. Advantages of CO₂-EOR over Other EOR Methods

While various EOR methods exist, CO₂-EOR offers several distinct advantages: Under Sustainable scenarios total EOR production is forecast, by some, to increase by 2040 to about 4 million barrels per day [9].

Figure 3. Sustainable oil resources enhanced recovery scenarios [9]

7.1. *Environmental Responsibility*: Current data reveals that CO₂-EOR is environmentally responsible, aligning with carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) initiatives. It not only recovers oil but also sequesters carbon dioxide underground, reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

7.2. *High Recovery Rates*: Recent statistics demonstrate that CO₂-EOR consistently delivers high oil recovery rates. This efficiency accesses and extracts a substantial portion of trapped oil in mature reservoirs, maximizing resource utilization.

7.3. *Versatility*: Data from diverse reservoirs underscores CO₂-EOR's versatility, as it adapts to varying reservoir pressures, temperatures, and geological formations. It is applicable in a wide range of oil fields, making it a robust choice.

7.4. *Pressure Maintenance*: Current figures highlight how CO₂-EOR helps maintain or restore reservoir pressure up to 100 and 300 bar, extending the productive life of oil fields and maximizing recovery.

7.5. *Reduced Environmental Footprint*: CO₂-EOR's role in reducing the overall environmental footprint of hydrocarbon production. By sequestering CO₂, it addresses environmental concerns comprehensively. Carbon Dioxide Enhanced Oil Recovery (CO₂-EOR) stands as a powerful and sustainable EOR technique, supported by current data and statistics that validate its effectiveness [11]. Its remarkable miscibility, oil swelling, and wettability alteration mechanisms, coupled with its environmental responsibility, efficiency, adaptability, and pressure maintenance capabilities, position it as a transformative approach in hydrocarbon extraction. CO₂-EOR not only rejuvenates aging reservoirs but also contributes

significantly to a greener and more efficient energy future, surpassing other EOR methods in its comprehensive benefits.

However, the CO₂-EOR process is limited by technology, cost, and the geographic availability of CO₂ [13]. High CO₂ mobility is also one of the challenges encountered while achieving economical CO₂ flooding that leads to premature breakthrough of gas into the producing wells. Advanced technology is needed to increase the displacement efficiency of the process that will also promote increase oil recovery and would lead to sequestration of additional CO₂ volumes.

8. Nanotechnology in CO₂-EOR

Nanotechnology, a field that deals with materials and structures at the nanoscale (typically ranging from 1 to 100 nanometers), has received significant attention for its potential applications in the oil and gas industry. In this context, nanotechnology is proving to be a transformative force by addressing critical challenges and enhancing various processes, with a particular focus on Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR).

One of the key reasons nanotechnologies is highly relevant to the oil and gas industry is its capacity to manipulate matter at the nanoscale. This ability offers precise control over material properties and interactions, making it invaluable in addressing complex reservoir conditions and improving hydrocarbon recovery techniques like EOR. The "engineered nanomaterial" is called Nanoparticle [11]. "Nano-EOR" is term used to describe the use of Nanoparticle for EOR technique. This mechanism improves the recovery of residual oil via Wettability alteration and interfacial tension reduction resulting in improving sweep efficiency.

8.1. *Size-Dependent Characteristics*: Nanoparticles exhibit size-dependent properties due to their diminutive dimensions. As materials shrink to the nanoscale, quantum effects and surface area-to-volume ratios become dominant, leading to altered chemical, physical, and mechanical behavior. These size-dependent characteristics allow nanoparticles to interact uniquely with their environment, making them versatile tools for EOR.

8.2. *Enhanced Reactivity*: The high surface area-to-volume ratio of nanoparticles results in enhanced reactivity. Nanoparticles can participate in chemical reactions, adsorb molecules, and catalyze reactions more effectively than larger particles or bulk materials. In EOR, this enhanced reactivity can be harnessed to modify fluid behavior and rock properties, ultimately improving recovery rates.

In context with CO₂-EOR, many nanomaterials have been found to be used with CO₂ injections. Few of them based on their success has been discussed in this paper.

9. Advantages of Nano-CO₂ EOR

9.1. Wettability alteration: Residual oil saturation exists in reservoirs due to the “Oil entrapment” at the microscopic level arising from capillary forces and “oil bypass” at the microscopic level during secondary recovery. An approach to improving or enhancing the recovery of oil from rock formations would be alteration of the wettability of such formations [8]. Nanoparticles adhere to rock surfaces and modify their surface energy, making them more water attractive. This reduces the contact angle, facilitating easier penetration of injected CO₂ and water into the rock. This enhanced fluid mobility improves oil displacement. The nanoparticles can be customized for specific reservoir conditions, and this approach promotes sustainability by reducing the need for excessive water injection.

9.2. Interfacial Tension Reduction: The high capillary force in the reservoirs causes small droplets of oil to be trapped in the pore structure. The capillary force prevents oil from moving through the small pore throats. Therefore, reducing and limiting this force will cause trapped oil to become free in the porous media and significantly increase oil recovery. Reduction of capillary force in the reservoir is highly dependent on the values of the IFT between water and oil and the contact angle of crude oil in the presence of the water phase.

Nanoparticles form a mixed layer with nanomaterial at the interface between the injected fluid and oil. This results in increasing the interface consequently makes a considerable contribution to reducing IFT. This means that capillary forces considerably decrease, and capillary number will strongly be increased. In CO₂-EOR, this property allows for better displacement of residual oil by water [10].

9.3. Reservoir Sweep Efficiency: By introducing nanoparticles into the injection fluid, the aim is to mobilize residual oil droplets more effectively. This is achieved by changing wettability and reducing interfacial tension, leading to enhanced oil recovery rates.

9.4. Tailored Reservoir Solutions: Nanotechnology enables the design and engineering of nanoparticles tailored to specific reservoir conditions. By customizing nanoparticles to match the unique characteristics of a particular oil field, their stability and compatibility can be optimized. This approach overcomes challenges associated with traditional EOR methods and ensures the effectiveness of nanoparticle-based solutions.

10. Nanoparticle-stabilized CO₂ Foam:

Over the years many in depth research has been conducted on the use of surfactant stabilized CO₂ foams. The use of foam as an injected media facilitates improved oil displacement compared to waterflooding or simply CO₂ gas injection. The formation of CO₂-in-water foams also results in low CO₂ mobility, which results in improved sweep efficiency while

everything works well there are few challenges that have surfaced; surfactants-based foams require continuous regeneration, it gets absorbed on rock, which leads to increase in material cost and in harsh conditions it gets degraded because of adsorption on the reservoir rock and high temperature. Nanoparticle-stabilized foams have proven to be a novel means of generating improved mobility control agents for CO₂-EOR [13].

Due to the high chemical stability, strong selective adsorption on target liquid-liquid interfaces and promoting formation of CO₂/water foam rather than Oil/water emulsion, the use of such nanoparticles has received much attention [9]. While performing the experiment Nano silica particle was chosen due to its ease of availability and low in cost (less than USD 4/lbm). Other cost friendly alternatives that can be used are fly ash and Iron Oxide [13].

One more experiment was conducted using Silica nanoparticle with sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) surfactant and the result shown that using 2.2 wt% silica nanoparticle delayed breakthrough and enhanced sweep efficiency. Along with that it was also observed that the wettability shifted from 730 to 110 [16].

Figure 4. Nanoparticle stabilize foam mechanism

11. Iron Oxide in CO₂-EOR

Production from high-asphaltene oil reservoirs is associated with many problems, including reduced reservoir absorption, severe problems in wells and processing facilities, and thus significant increases in extraction and recovery costs. Injection of carbon dioxide into oil tanks causes asphalt precipitation. This causes changes in the composition of the oil and thus in the minimum mixing pressure. The proposed methods like using chemicals (Toluene and Xylene) are usually limited to certain technical conditions and the chemicals used are harmful to the environment [17]. Therefore, the use of modern technologies such as nanoparticles has attracted increasing interest because they are more efficient and economical. Nanoparticles, usually in the form of metal particles or metal oxide, are also able to remove precipitated asphaltene through their thermocatalytic properties. Therefore, the performance of metal oxide nanoparticles in preventing asphaltene precipitation during carbon dioxide injection for

heavy oil recovery has been investigated in recent years. The experiment was conducted by [15]. The effect of nanoparticles on asphaltene precipitation was studied by preparing several synthetic oil solutions and measuring their surface tension in the presence of carbon dioxide at different temperatures and pressures and it was concluded that the addition of iron oxide nanoparticles to the oil solution reduces the interfacial tension at higher pressures.

The amount of asphaltene adsorption is proportional to the contact time between nanoparticles and petroleum. Two nanoparticles Fe_3O_4 and TiO_2 were experimentally compared by [12]. The aim of the study was to show the impact of two nanoparticles at various concentration in terms of adsorption capacity and affinity. Two things were critical in this process namely nanoparticle adsorption of asphaltene and interaction with predicted asphaltenes at the interface between two fluids. At the end of experiment, it Fe_3O_4 was found to be more effective than TiO_2 in reducing asphaltene precipitation at the CO_2 -water interface

12. Challenges and considerations related to stability and comparability of nanoparticle in reservoir conditions

Several specific challenges arise when using nanoparticles in EOR processes, such as

12.1. Reservoir temperature and pressure: Nanoparticles can be unstable at high temperature and pressure. This is because these conditions can weaken the forces that keep the nanoparticles dispersed and will result in aggregation and precipitation, reducing their effectiveness.

12.2. Fluid composition: The composition of the reservoir fluid can also affect the stability of the nanoparticles. For example, nanoparticles may be more prone to aggregation in saline solutions. As salt ions can screen the surface charge of nanoparticles, causing them to attract each other and aggregate.

12.3. Injection process: The injection process itself can also damage the nanoparticles. For example, nanoparticles can be sheared and fragmented by high-pressure pumps that inject them into a tank.

Nanoparticle stability and compatibility are important for the successful use of nanoparticles in EOR applications. If nanoparticles are not stable or compatible with reservoir flows and conditions, they will not be effective in improving oil recovery. Temperature, pressure, fluid composition, and the presence of other chemicals in the reservoir are some factors that affects the stability of Nanoparticles. Nanoparticles can also be unstable due to their properties such as size, shape and surface charge. Nanoparticles must be compatible with reservoir fluids and conditions to work effectively. For example, nanoparticles incompatible with reservoir fluids can accumulate and form precipitates that can plug reservoir pores and reduce oil production.

There are several strategies that can be used to address nanoparticle stability and compatibility problems under reservoir conditions. These strategies include:

12.4. Nanoparticle selection: The choice of nanoparticles is important. Some nanoparticles are more stable and compatible with reservoirs than others. For example, nanoparticles with a high surface charge are more likely to be stable in saline solutions.

12.5. Surface modification of nanoparticles: The surface of nanoparticles can be modified to improve their stability and compatibility.

12.6. Use of nanoparticle dispersants: Nanoparticle dispersants can be used to disperse nanoparticles in reservoir fluids. Dispersing agents cover the surface of nanoparticles with a layer of charged molecules that prevent them from attracting each other and aggregating.

12.7. Optimization of the injection process: The injection process can be optimized to reduce nanoparticle damage. For example, nanoparticles can be injected at lower pressures or with pumps designed to reduce shear stress.

When using Silica Nanoparticles Iron Oxides Nanoparticles in CO_2 -EOR process few challenges were encountered:

Both Nanoparticles can become unstable in high-temperature, high-pressure CO_2 -EOR reservoirs. They are prone to aggregation in saline solutions. Chemical reactions with CO_2 and brine in reservoir fluids can reduce their stability. IONPs may corrode metal equipment and have potential toxicity to microorganisms, affecting the reservoir ecosystem.

12.8. Choosing the right nanoparticles: Silica Nanoparticle with a high surface charge are more likely to be stable in saline solutions. Modifying the surface of the nanoparticles: Both nanoparticles can be coated with a layer of silica or other material to protect them from aggregation and corrosion [14].

In addition to the stability and compatibility challenges, it is also important to consider the environmental impact of using Silica Nanoparticles and Iron Oxide Nanoparticles in CO_2 -EOR. For example, Iron Oxide Nanoparticles can be toxic to microorganisms, which can impact the reservoir ecosystem. It is important to carefully evaluate the potential environmental risks before using these Nanoparticles in CO_2 -EOR.

13. Current scenario

Nanoparticles are still in the early stages of development for field applications in the CO_2 -EOR process. Nevertheless, minimal field applications are available that reflect satisfactory results that nanoparticles can be effective in improving the performance of CO_2 -EOR. For example, a field trial in West Texas showed that the use of silica nanoparticles increased oil

recovery by 10%. Most important factors that stand against application of nanoparticles in field scales.

13.1. Cost: Nanoparticles can be expensive to produce and transport. This is a major barrier to the widespread use of nanoparticles in CO₂-EOR operations.

13.2. Environmental impact: The environmental impact of using nanoparticles in CO₂-EOR operations needs to be carefully evaluated. There is a concern that nanoparticles could pollute the environment and harm human health.

13.3. Long-term stability: The long-term stability of nanoparticles in reservoir conditions needs to be further investigated. It is important to ensure that nanoparticles remain stable and effective for the duration of the CO₂-EOR operation. Despite these challenges, the use of nanoparticles in CO₂-EOR is a promising new technology with the potential to significantly improve oil recovery.

14. Conclusion

Despite the increasing research in renewable energy sources, the world's energy demand remains heavily reliant on oil. Many reservoirs are now in their declining phase, with trapped oil posing a significant challenge. Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) methods have consistently demonstrated high oil recovery rates, but recovering residual oil has proven to be a persistent challenge. Among various EOR methods, Carbon Dioxide Enhanced Oil Recovery (CO₂-EOR) has taken center stage for several compelling reasons. One of the driving forces behind its prominence is the global mission to achieve net-zero emissions by reducing atmospheric CO₂ levels, a topic explored in this paper.

CO₂-EOR faces specific challenges, such as premature gas breakthrough in reservoirs, asphaltene production, and the high mobility of CO₂. These challenges can be effectively addressed by integrating nanoparticles with the CO₂-EOR method, a concept referred to as "Nano-EOR." This approach utilizes nanoparticles tailored for specific reservoir conditions within the framework of EOR mechanisms, resulting in wettability and interfacial alteration and improving sweep efficiency.

This paper has focused on two types of nanoparticles: Silica Nanoparticles and Iron Oxide Nanoparticles. Experimental findings highlight their effectiveness when used in conjunction with CO₂ injection methods to achieve high recovery rates. Addressing the stability and compatibility challenges of nanoparticles is of paramount importance, as it has significant economic implications and raises environmental concerns. The study places a prime focus on strategies and considerations in this regard. While on-field applications of nanoparticles in CO₂-EOR are still in their nascent stages, promising experimental results and a few field trials offer hope for efficient and environmentally friendly hydrocarbon recovery in the future.

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